

3-7 Oct. Harvesting began on 23 Oct and ended on 25 Nov.

All entries had submergence tolerance and elongation ability. Plant height, which reflects elongation ability in relation to water depth, was significantly different among entries (see table).

Tillers and panicles/m² were quite numerous, but entries did not significantly differ. *Glaberrima* cultivars had a high incidence of grain shattering,

which might be a major factor in their low grain yield.

Yields did not significantly differ among entries. None of the test entries outyielded FARO 14. This contrasts the previous year's results when DM17, DA29, and Maiada outyielded FARO 14 by producing more than 5 t/ha.

Cultivars DA29, Maiada, and *O. glaberrima* mature 3-5 wk earlier than FARO 14. The earliness of DA29 and

Maiada makes them suitable for deepwater areas where flood duration is short and the harmattan cold and wind makes cultivating long-duration varieties risky.

Their acceptability, based on phenotype and grain quality as determined with the *Standard evaluation system for rice*, is excellent. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—tidal wetlands

Netravathi (KKP-6): a promising rice variety for coastal lowlands of Karnataka, India

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Rice is grown on more than 150,000 ha in coastal Karnataka during kharif (monsoon) season. Phalguna, the variety commonly grown in lowlands that are partially submerged during heavy rains, has problems with spikelet sterility and is susceptible to neck blast (BI).

IET2886 was crossed with Red Annapurna, and KKP-6 was identified and released as Netravathi in 1990. Netravathi outyielded Phalguna (Table 1) in multilocation trials conducted at Mangalore and Brahmavar. Leaf and neck BI incidence was less in Netravathi than in Phalguna. Netravathi also resists gall midge (GM) (Table 2). It has a

Table 1. Performance of Netravathi (KKP-6) in yield trials,^a Karnataka, India, 1983-87.

Trial	Year	Location	Replications (no.)	Plot size (m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	
					KKP-6	Phalguna
GM-resistant varietal trial	1983	Agricultural Research Station, Mangalore	3	1.5 × 3.0	4.9	3.2
GM-resistant varietal trial	1984	Agricultural Research Station, Mangalore	4	4.6 × 2.0	4.4	3.5
GM-resistant varietal trial	1985	Regional Research Station, Brahmavar	4	6.2 × 1.8	4.3	4.4
Rice varietal trial	1987	Regional Research Station, Brahmavar	3	4.5 × 2.0	4.7	3.6

^aFertilized at the rate of 75-75-90 kg NPK/ha.

growth duration of about 135-140 d and is 104 cm tall. It can withstand submergence for 5-7 d.

Netravathi yields about 11% more grain than does Phalguna. Netravathi has less spikelet sterility than Phalguna, and it is suitable for parboiling. The variety is recommended for lowland areas during kharif. ■

Table 2. Reaction of Netravathi (KKP-6) to BI and GM in coastal Karnataka, India.^a

Variety	Leaf BI (% affected)	Neck BI (% affected)	GM (% affected)
Netravathi	1.3	5.1	0.00
Phalguna	3.4	24.5	0.75

^aMean of four trials.